

Transfer learning for metamodel construction to enable uncertainty quantifications in crash design based on scarce data availability

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Abstract

This work investigates the possibility to obtain metamodels to use in uncertainty quantification when little to no data points are available. This scenario occurs in the early-stage vehicle design for crashworthiness. As long as a suitable model of the new design is not available, the data from predecessor designs might be of aid. The aim of this study is to compute the metamodel of a crash box whose geometrical features differ partially from those of past comparable structures. To reach this goal, a transfer learning (TL) method is investigated. The finite element simulations data of the past crash boxes constitute the source domain; the few available simulations of the product of interest, instead, create the target domain. The TL method learns the basic knowledge from the source domain and then is readjusted based on the target domain. This approach constitutes an attractive starting point for the investigation of diverse types of system uncertainties. Overall, the presented method is considered especially helpful for engineers in the early-stage design process.

1 Introduction

The development of a vehicle is a complex task. Car manufacturers need to satisfy strict safety requirements. Assessing vehicle safety in an early stage of development, they need to face the challenge of low data availability.

For instance, this scenario occurs in the early-stage vehicle design, as the ultimate geometrical and material data of the product are still not available. In recent years, crash finite element (FE) simulations have become essential for automotive R&D. As they are faster, sufficiently repeatable, and more cost-efficient than hardware tests, FE simulations currently drive the design process.

Regardless the advantage of being monetary cheaper than experimental tests, FE simulations still require high effort from a computational point of view. For instance, investigating reliability and robustness designs could become infeasible with respect to time. To overcome this difficulty, metamodels are often proposed. Allowing faster output generation, these low-fidelity approaches are regarded as an efficient way to further relieve the computing budget and improve the design efficiency of simulation-based problems [1].

Despite the showed advantages, the procedure that leads to the implementation of a metamodel is often hard. It requires numerous computationally expensive simulations. This becomes even more difficult when, in the early-stage design, still little-to-no insights of the product are available.

Nonetheless, the availability of a metamodel is crucial. A task worthy of pursuit, in this context, is exploiting data coming from past development processes to infer knowledge on future situations. In the industry, most new product designs are obtained by partially modifying some existing ones and it is rare that entirely new

products have to be designed from scratch [2]. The aim of the present study is to harness information from past validation studies, extending them to forthcoming cases.

This paper investigates whether information drawn from past versions of one original product can be used to give prediction on the metamodel representing a new product version. As an attractive alternative to expert knowledge, transfer learning (TL) approach comes to be suitable for the application at hand: as long as a suitable model of the new design is only partially accessible, the data and models from predecessor designs might be of aid. In the following, the corresponding approach will be presented.

2 State of the art in transfer learning

Nowadays, the first vehicle development process phases are mainly characterized by the virtual assessment of crashworthiness, by means of the finite element simulations [3, 4]. Verification and validation of the FE simulations, in order to allow optimization and robustness analysis, are trending research topics.

In the early stage design of a product, data coming from past similar development studies can become appealing. Therefore, as an attractive alternative to expert knowledge, TL approach comes to be suitable for the current application. In the following, a literature review of the TL technique is presented.

The field of transfer learning (TL) examines and develops methods using knowledge acquired from previously solved source tasks in order to more efficiently solve new target tasks [5]. The application at hand, crash validation studies, can benefit from such capability; the large availability of predecessor designs data becomes of aid for the new design.

Authors in [6] state that, although traditional machine learning (ML) technology has been successfully applied in certain practical applications, its ideal scenario still requires abundant labelled training instances. However, collecting sufficient training data is often expensive, time-consuming, or even unrealistic in many scenarios. TL becomes a promising way to solve the problem. While traditional ML trains every model from scratch, TL reuses a model or knowledge for another related task.

TL helps ML techniques to relax the need of collecting big amounts of highly reliable data. Under the assumption that the two domains are similar, TL relies on extracting the basic knowledge from the source domain and applying it to fulfil the required task in the target domain [7]. The TL model is, in other words, first trained on source domain - or low-fidelity - data, from which it learns the core relationships, and then, readapted to the few high-fidelity data of the target domain. Authors of [8] present three different ways to perform the domain adaptation: the bi-fidelity TL — BFTL — 1 and 2, and the bi-fidelity weighted learning — BFWL. In BFTL-1 the uppermost hidden layer of a network trained using the low-fidelity dataset is fine-tuned using the high-fidelity dataset; in BFTL-2, a small network is added to model the map between the output estimated by the low-fidelity and its high-fidelity counterpart; in BFWL, the parameters of the low-fidelity NN are modified according to data generated via a high-fidelity trained Gaussian process. The study shows the efficiency of BFWL in diverse study cases and remarks the difficulty of using BFTL-2 when small amount of high fidelity samples is given. An extensive overview of TL can be found in [6, 7, 9].

Many literature sources focus on the application of TL in the fields of medical imaging, email spam or speech recognition - [6, 7, 10]. As of yet, industrial applications of TL appear to be sparsely reported. However, few studies have highlighted the strong capabilities of this technique in industrial scenarios.

Nowadays, the majority of the recent TL studies focus on anomaly detection and fault diagnosis. Authors in [11] use it to support designers in the initial set-up of the injection moulding procedure: by means of only a small amount of experimental data, they manage to predict quality-related criteria for process parameters; in [12] and [13], TL is applied for bearing and gearing fault diagnosis, respectively. Focusing on defect detection and image segmentation, [14] shows another industrial application of TL for quality management.

What all these applications have in common is that they require only a few data on the target domain to result in good predictions. This makes the TL technique attractive for the application at hand, being the vehicle crash a scenario in which simulations play an integral part and the experiments are scarce, yet fundamental.

3 Method

The implemented TL method is applied to FE simulations of crash box geometries undergoing drop tower tests. Specifically, two cases are investigated: in the first, the source domain contains two types of crash box geometry, including the one of the target domain; in the second, the source domain is limited to a single type of geometry, different from the target domain design. As assessment method, models exclusively trained on the target data are implemented.

Our method is divided into two steps. First, the data collection process; then, the implementation of the TL algorithm. The data collection process is further divided into two parts: running the FE simulations, and using the obtained results to generate further data. As a practical application, the entire framework is applied to crash box structures.

Figure 1: Single- and double-cell geometries.

Figure 2: Geometrical features.

Six steel crash boxes are selected; the geometries are of two types: single- and double-cell, Figure 1. The geometries differ in terms of: number of cells, height, width, height-to-width ratio, cross-sectional area, and total length. For an extensive explanation of the cited geometrical features, refer to Figure 2. Five of these geometries are selected to represent the source domain; the remaining one stands for the target domain.

For each crash box, explicit FE simulations are performed using the R9.3.0 version of the LS-DYNA solver. The specimen is positioned vertically and fixed at the bottom, and a rigid barrier moves towards it in the longitudinal direction with initial velocity of 56 km/h. The mass of the rigid barrier is set according to the crash box geometry, producing 4 folds in the deformed configuration. Simulations are run with varying values of the crash box wall thickness in a range of $\pm 5\%$ from the nominal value. Latin Hypercube technique is used to sample the design variable. The output quantity of interest is always the mean value of the obtained force-displacement curve, namely, the mean crushing force.

Up to this point of the data collection process, each performed simulation is represented by three values: the crash box design (i.e. A, B, C, D, E, and F), the input wall thickness, and the output mean crushing force. The values are then shifted and scaled to zero mean and unit variance, as preprocessing for ML.

Before moving to the TL implementation, further data is generated to enrich the datasets. We create one predictor per crash box using, for the sake of diversity, linear regression or Gaussian process. Following the assumption that the target domain data are not sufficient to compute even an adequate predictor, the data generation is only performed for the source domain geometries. Finally, we enrich each individual dataset with the crash box specific geometrical features. These choices lead to a large, diverse, and exhaustive dataset, ready to be used as source domain.

After the data collection process, the TL algorithm is implemented in Python 3.8.3 [15] following [16]. The procedure is divided into two parts: first, we train the NN based on the source domain data. These data, both

from the FE simulations and predictions, are considered here to be low-fidelity, as they do not accurately represent the target domain; second, the same NN is adapted to the target domain data. We decide to perform the domain adaptation updating the architecture of the last few hidden layers with a procedure similar to BFTL-1 [8]. The ML algorithms of this study are implemented using the high-level deep learning API Keras library [17].

Figure 3: Transfer learning implementation workflow.

The domain adaptation workflow is outlined in Figure 3. We substitute the last layer of the original NN - Figure 3a - with a new architecture - Figure 3b -, according to the target domain data. Afterwards, we set the network gains. To achieve this goal, we perform two training processes: in the first, the gains of the reused initial layers are frozen and only the gains of the newly inserted layers are set according to the target domain data - Figure 3c; in the second training process, the same target data are used to fine-tune the gains of the whole network, including those of the reused initial layers - Figure 3d. After the second training process, the procedure is concluded.

The method is then repeated considering the second application case: in this phase of the work, the source domain is limited to only single-cell crash box geometries, while the target domain is still represented by a double-cell crash box — Figure 1. A new initial NN is implemented and trained on the limited source domain; next, again the first and second training processes are performed.

Finally, for comparison purposes, two assessment methods are implemented. We train both, a linear regression model and a NN exclusively on the target domain data. This choice follows the approach of [8] and well represents the assumption of the low availability of data. With no exploitation of the data coming from previous designs — namely, the source domain — these two methods show the prediction that would be obtained when only the target domain data are assumed to be available.

The quality of the results of this study is evaluated in terms of the coefficient of determination R^2 . Considering a sample of n data points, $Y = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n]$ is the vector of observed values, \bar{y} is its mean value and $\hat{Y} = [\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \dots, \hat{y}_n]$ is the vector of the predicted values. The R^2 is defined as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: Transfer learning results.

Compared to the mean squared error (MSE), which could get more or less pronounced based on whether the data is scaled or not, the R^2 tends to give a better picture of the absolute quality of the results.

4 Results

The NN trained on the source domain data consisted of 4 hidden layers with 70 neurons each, and ReLU activation function. The preliminary investigation on the original network showed an R^2 equal to 0.99997. Subsequently, this architecture was modified according to the target domain data.

Following the approach explained in the previous section, new architectures were selected for, respectively, $N_t = [40, 30, 20, 10]$ target domain data points. Each time, the last hidden layer of the original neural network was substituted with a new composition of hidden layers and neurons per layers. For validation, always the same $N_{vt} = 10$ target data points were used to assess the network performance. Figure 4a shows the results of this process. The R^2 coefficients were obtained for 30 independent, random initializations of the network parameters (prior to the first training process) and with fixed training and validation datasets.

The coefficients of determination were collected both at the end of the first — dotted line — and second — solid line — training process. Moreover, results were reported for different numbers of epochs. The red lines with squared and circled markers refer to training processes of 1000 epochs; the blue lines with triangular markers point out the results obtained with 4000 epochs.

Figure 4b shows the results of the second phase of the work, where a limited source domain is considered. In this case, only 2 hidden layers with 50 neurons each resulted to be sufficient to reach a quality of the performance of $R^2 = 0.99988$. Again, the NN architecture was modified with the two training processes to fit the data coming from the target domain.

Figure 5 compares the previous results with the two implemented assessment methods. Here, the results obtained at the end of the second training process for the case of 4000 epochs are plotted against the NN and the linear regression trained on exclusively the target domain data points.

5 Discussion

TL allows to transfer the knowledge from a source domain to a target domain. In this study, the source domain is represented by previously developed products; the role of the target domain is taken by a new

Figure 5: Comparison between the transfer learning results with those of the assessment methods.

product of interest, considered to be in the early stage design. TL fills the knowledge gap in the target domain by exploiting the high availability of the source domain data.

In industry, as explained above, early on in the development, when the final characteristics of a product are not yet entirely defined, the availability of a metamodel is crucial. It is often true that, although information on the new product of interest are missing, there is a high availability of those from previous already developed versions. The versions can sometimes differ in terms of geometrical features (e.g. extrusions, holes). The method developed in this study allows to exploit the information from past geometrically comparable products to estimate the behaviour of the new one.

The present work also aims to remark the different cost associated to the data collection. Data constituting the source domain are easy to be collected: FE simulations or metamodels from past developed product versions are considered to be readily available. In contrast, target domain data are hardly available.

From Figure 4a it can be noticed that, overall, the method leads to good predictions (e.g. $R^2 = 0.99851$ for $N_t = 40$ target data points). Moreover, one can observe that, the fewer target domain data points are available, the more the quality of the prediction decreases. This fits with the general expectation: with less information from the target domain, it becomes more difficult to compute a good prediction.

Figure 4a also underlines the significant improvement obtained from performing the second training process in the case of 1000 epochs. This behaviour suggests that, increasing the number of epochs in the first training process, the network could be provided with enough time to re-adapt its gains in order to already give good results. This hypothesis is supported by the good results quality obtained in the first training case with 4000 epochs, represented by the blue dotted line in Figure 4a. The vicinity between the two blue triangle lines suggests that the second training process seems indeed to be ineffective, as the improvement showed from the dotted to the solid line is unperceivable (i.e. 1.3% of difference in the case of $N_t = 10$ target data points). The quality of the results is satisfying already at the end of the first training process with 4000 epochs, with a final $R^2 = 0.98545$ for $N_t = 40$ target data points. Overall, results show that a good prediction quality can be achieved with a sufficient number of epochs in the first training process. Moreover, the second training process does not worsen the prediction.

Figure 4b, obtained in the case of a limited source domain, shows similar results. The choice of limiting the source domain to only single-cell crash box structures increases the geometrical differences between the source and the target domain designs. This situation is especially interesting for industrial applications. In this case, the same behaviour with the original source domain case can be observed. Specifically, R^2 decreases with decreasing available target data points and increases from the first to the second training process in the case of 1000 epochs. Moving from 1000 to 4000 epochs, R^2 increases. The difference between dotted and solid line in the case of 4000 epochs is negligible. Again, this leads to the conclusion of the second training process being ineffective under the assumption of a sufficient number of epochs in the first training process.

Figure 5 compares the TL results with two reference methods for the sake of confirming the approach. For a high number of available target data points, the TL method does not provide significant advance with respect to the assessment methods. One possible reason of this behaviour can be found in the linearity of the observed phenomenon.

TL was performed here by modifying the architecture of the last layers of the network, while keeping one of the first layers fixed. [18] explains that the initial layers use to capture generic non-linear features, while the later ones focus more on the specific task at hand. This statement may be explicative of the results obtained in this study. The wall thickness to mean crushing force relationship is linear for crash box structures. Therefore, the linear regression or the NN are likely to give good predictions even when a low number of target data points are available.

With respect to the literature, the current work introduces a novel aspect. In [8], authors show how the TL can easily serve as a method for metamodel construction for uncertainty quantification. There, the authors train the network on low-fidelity data and readapt its gains to a few high-fidelity points. Both low- and high-fidelity data are drawn from the same physical system. This study, in contrast, introduces the possibility of referring to multiple comparable but different physical systems.

The role of the high-fidelity data is taken by the few available data points coming from the product of interest. The information from slightly different designs is instead regarded as low-fidelity. A particular point to be addressed is the way the differences between the crash box designs have been represented: in this work, geometrical features (i.e wall thickness, number of cells, height, width, height-to-width ratio, cross sectional area and total length) were used. The simplicity of the studied geometry allows these features to be sufficient for an adequate objective distinction between the products. However, whenever more complex products geometries come into play, more sophisticated geometry classification methods need to be investigated.

6 Conclusion

The results of the study show the attractive TL capability of transferring the knowledge from a source to a target domain. The quality of the prediction decreases with fewer target data points. Moreover, the quality of the obtained results is comparable to the one of two assessment methods, both trained on only target domain data. These conclusions have been obtained both in the case of the original and limited source domain.

From this, we confirm that, with an appropriate description of the domains, TL is a valid alternative to expert knowledge for the metamodel construction in cases where little-to-no data are available. This initial study shows the promising predictive capability of the method.

With respect to literature TL studies, we have here introduced the possibility of moving the knowledge from a specific — geometrical — space to another. Nonetheless, TL has been here applied to a simple study case. The method, catching a non-linear intrinsic relationship, is still expected to show its entire potential when applied to more complex study cases. In non-linear cases, TL is awaited to perform better than any method trained only on target domain data.

We see TL as an interesting tool for metamodel prediction in the near future. Specifically, as preliminarily showed in this study, when required to catch the complex physics of a new product starting from information of geometrically similar design versions. This work also opens up the possibility to include experimental data of the target structure beyond just simulations, moving thus towards a grey-box approach. The final outlook expected from this work is to provide engineers with another useful tool to support their expertise and automatize the early-stage development operations.

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